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DEVELOPMENT: THE MEDIATING ROLE OF
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PSYCHOLOGICAL DEPRESSION

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Impact of Physical Education and Creative Self-Efficacy on Personality Development: The Mediating Role of Students Self-Perception and Psychological Depression

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Abstract

This study analyses the effect of physical education and creative self-efficacy on the personality development, and specifically on mediation of self-perception and psychological depression of the students among the students in learning facilities in Punjab, Pakistan. The study is based on perception that physical education is also relevant to the emotional stability, social competence and formation of the character and that the creative self-efficacy will increase the confidence that students have in their capabilities to come up with ideas, resolve issues, and communicate their thoughts in an effective way. All these combined are

likely to enhance positive personality characteristics like resilience, adaptability, openness and self-discipline. The study explores the influence of self-perception of students as the psychological process that allows involvement in the physical education and trust in creative skills to shape personality. Thus, survey research design has been used to collect the data from students hailing from the selection institutions in the particular region to analyze the variables and extract the desired outcome for reaching the desired conclusion. The statistical methods were used to compare direct and indirect correlations among variables, to find out whether the self-perception strengthens, and psychological depression diminishes the positive effect of physical education and creative self-efficacy on the personality results. It is hypothesized that findings will underscore fact that involvement in physical education and greater scores of creative self-efficacies have positive correlation with personality development and that these associations are largely mediated by perceptions of the self and psychological well-being in students. The study

also has an impact on education and psychological literature as it provides full-fledged model that covers interaction between physical, cognitive, emotional factors to influence the personality of students. It has practical implications on educators and policymakers to come up with supportive learning conditions that lead to the physical exercise, creativity and mental health provisions, eventually produce essential and strong individuals within institutions.

Keywords: Physical Education, Creative Self-Efficacy, Personality Development, Students Self-Perception, Psychological Depression & Mediation

INTRODUCTION

The effects of physical education and creative self-efficacy on the development of personalities, and mediating part played by self-perception and psychological depression of students, includes several psychological and educational constructs. Such relations can be supported by different theories, which associate physical activity, self-efficacy, self-perception, and mental health with personality development [1]. The creative self-efficacy in terms of personality development, as it may contribute to stronger confidence and desire of student to use creativity in solving problems to cultivate resilience, adaptability and openness [2]. It stresses on role of self-abilities in success of tasks and routs the challenge capability of being creative in the production of creative product [3]. Assistance with gaining confidence about control over physical activities, may be converted into elevated self-efficacy, that can also mobilize self-efficacy as there is the chance to get down to physical challenges.

When applied to students, their attitude towards their work in physical education and creative assignments can shape their self-image, added to personality aspects like confidence, openness to experience and creativity. According to the literature, individuals create attitudes and beliefs concerning themselves through observing their behavior [4]. The self-perception of the students can greatly affect their personalities as either positive or negative, playing the mediating role, it tends to either have a positive or a negative effect on shaping the personality, in case of the lack of physical activity and the lack of creative activity [5]. The positive self-perception encourages such characteristics as self-esteem and confidence whereas negative self-perception impairs the development of personality [6]. The psychological depression may have negative consequences on the well-being of students, self-esteem and socialization, impairing the formation of positive personality characteristics.

The consequences of poor self-perception be inadequacy, high susceptibility to psychological depression, that has negative effect on developing personality. Depression may result in certain characteristics such as low self-confidence, cynicism and withdrawal, as the result of prolonged depression [7]. This renders psychological depression as the significant mediator in the effect of physical education and acts as negative mediator, where the heavy levels of depression as result of low self-perception hinder personality growth, whereas low levels of depression may support positive growth [8]. The depression is frequently caused by the negative self-conception and the lack of confidence, creative sphere struggle mitigates or increases the effects of depression on the personality development over involvement, teamwork and resilience [9]. The environment of the physical education stimulates students to acquire personality features of the conscientiousness and emotional stability.

The physical well-being is not the only result of physical education, as it leads to development of psychology and social aspects of character. The self-confidence developed in process of social interactions and physical education achievements helps in the development of the personality [10]. Therefore, positive feedback improves self-perception, which encourages personality traits, such as extroversion and agreeableness that is linked with personality traits, such as openness to experience and innovation. Enhances self-esteem, social competence and mood control that are antecedents of personality development [11]. The students who feel the sense of creativity capabilities are likely to be involved in activities that would promote personal development and self-expression, develop a feeling of intelligence, which are vital in molding their personality [12]. Thus, creative work promotes problem solving and critical thinking, are essential aspects of the personality development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The self-image, and the way the students regard their performances and successes in the fields of physical and creative activities, is a key factor that contributes to efficacy of physical education and creative self-efficacy on personality development. Positive self-perception can be helpful to boost the positive effects of such activities, whereas negative self-perception worsens them [25]. The psychological depression may greatly influence ability of students to have positive outcomes of physical education and creative self-efficacy. It influences the motivation, engagement and effectiveness of students in aspects which may restrict their positive impact on the personality development [26]. The physical education and creative self-efficacy have complicated impact on personality

development, needs an encompassing well-being [27]. Physical education enables students to be exposed to physical activities that may improve and social skills, which are a part of personality development.

The students feel that they are good in physical activities or creative tasks and this aspect makes them strong in their confidence and motivation, that leads to healthy personality development. These effects may be obtained by positive self-perception that may strengthen positive effects that physical education and creative self-efficacy may have on personality development, it may be undermined by negative self-perception [28]. It is a crucial mediating factor between physical education, creative self-efficacy, negative emotions of personality development, feelings of failure shortage, stunting personality development [29]. The depression is normally caused by negative perception towards self, failure in artistic or physical activities, or social loneliness. A major consequence that may inhibit it develop is psychological depression [30]. Depressed students can have challenges in believing in creativity, which further undermines their self-image as well as personality development.

The possessions of physical education and creative self-efficacy on personality development is a multidimensional process by which students develop psychological strength, social competence as well as emotional balance [4]. Physical education is important in the formation of personality as it offers students an opportunity to work together, participate in physical activities, and be goal-oriented that are required towards the desired determinations for the outcomes [7]. The innovative efficacy of self, which is the concept that describes a viewpoint of the student in the ability to generate creative ideas and resolve problems in creative manner, further contributes to developing the personality as it stimulates the curiosity, autonomy and adaptability [10]. Having the higher creative self-efficacy, students will be more inclined to be proactive, seek alternative solutions, and react to the challenges in constructive ways that will make them more open and flexible for developments.

By attending routine, students gain discipline, stamina, leadership traits, and stress management skills which plays a key role in shaping a good personality [11]. The physical activity is equally known to drive emotional stability and increase self-confidence through physical health, and development of a sense of accomplishment, students take challenges with courage and optimism [13]. Positive self-perception enables the student to put their experiences into perspective in an empowering manner, that enhances self-esteem and gives the student the sense of belonging and meaningfulness. By establishing perception of themselves as competent

and worthy, students will become more active in the physical and academic environments, form positive interpersonal relationships, and stick towards personal goals [16]. This ideology promotes self-expression and critical thinking which helps the students to create the strong sense of self-identity and their personal competence.

Combined with the experiential learning climate offered by physical education, the creative self-efficacy helps to strengthen positive behavior patterns that favour holistic developments. The self-perception of the students is one of the key psychological processes, with the help of which physical education and creative self-efficacy can influence the development of personality [18]. The intervening influence of psychological depression explains significance of emotional health in achievement of the beneficial impacts of physical involvement and creative confidence [20]. Lessening psychological distress can result in the students enjoying more enthusiasm, resiliency, and emotional equilibrium, which makes them have more abilities to grow personally [21]. Self-perception consequently serves as a facilitator that will be used to translate participation and confidence into significant developmental outcomes, which will support positive attitudes and behaviors for outcomes.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The population of study comprises the entire elements (subjects) of research whose views are collected and analyzed on specific issues in specific context. Similarly, defining population clearly helps in understanding the scope and boundaries of research study in order to consider generalizability parameters. The characteristics and behaviors observed within population can often be generalized to a larger group/population through sampling as analysis of the entire population is not possible nor needed. The population (2890) of this study comprises students from selected higher education institutions in Punjab, Pakistan, while sample is selected through sampling formula. Similarly, convenient simple random technique was used to access the sample from entire population. This procedure helps in providing the clues for attaining the desired and leading outcomes. Thus, 350 questionnaires were physically distributed wherein 322 were thus recollected for analysis.

Data Collection & Analysis

The data collection and analysis are crucial phases in research process that aims to collect and analyze data to extract desired information and reaching conclusion. It includes collection of data through diverse sources (primary & secondary) and its analysis through (argumentation & statistical procedures) to reach desired conclusion and making decisions. The

secondary data will be collected through existing literature from different databases while primary data as collected through questionnaire via survey was analyzed through statistical procedures as per the nature of relationships. Consequently, this study used different required sources for the data collection and analysis. The secondary data was analyzed through argumentation process while primacy data was analyzed through different statistical procedures for attaining the data about the hypothesized relationships among the research variables that helped in reaching desired and leading research conclusions.

Questionnaire Design

The current study used survey approach to access the population through sample and collect the required data by using the questionnaire. The design of questionnaire is the critical aspect of research process, as it directly impacts quality and reliability of data collected. This will guide the selection of appropriate questions and ensure that the questionnaire collects relevant data as per research objectives. The common question types include closed-ended (Likert scale), open-ended (text response), and ranking questions. In this linking, scale about physical education be adapted from [11], creative self-efficacy from [14], students' self-perception from [19], psychological depression from [25], and personality development from [31], by using the 5-point Liker scale. The questionnaire is important in collecting the required information from the respondents of study through different statements for measuring the research variables as well as analyzing the variables for extracting the desired information for reaching the conclusions of the current research study.

RESULTS OF STUDY

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Physical Education	322	1.40	4.00	3.2775	.77941
Creative Self-Efficacy	322	1.30	4.00	3.7798	.78331
Students' Self-Perception	322	1.70	4.70	3.3484	.67373
Psychological Depression	322	1.60	4.00	3.4709	.73188
Personality Development	322	1.63	4.70	3.3503	.60376
Valid N (listwise)	322				

The descriptive statistics on the research leading variables contain important information on the variables regarding the sample, mean, minimum and maximum response rates of the respondents towards research variables and standard deviations used in the desired description of research issues under considerations. The findings and conclusions of analysis of this study offer critical information on measures that fall within reasonable limits and therefore greatly characterized the descriptions of the research variables in terms of mandated leading parameters. Thus, results of current study provide significant information concerning the research issues from different leading perspectives.

H1: There is positive association amid physical education, creative self-efficacy, student self-perception, depression and personality development (H1).

Correlation Analysis

		[1]	[1]	[1]	[1]	[1]
Physical Education [1]	Pearson Correlation	1	.372**	.404**	-.081	.546**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.146	.000
	N	322	322	322	322	322
Creative Self-Efficacy [1]	Pearson Correlation	.372**	1	.335**	-.135*	.469**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.015	.000
	N	322	322	322	322	322
Students' Self-Perception [1]	Pearson Correlation	.404**	.335**	1	-	.518**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.148**	.000
	N	322	322	322	322	322
Psychological Depression [1]	Pearson Correlation	-.081	-.135*	-	1	-.030
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.146	.015	.008		.587
	N	322	322	322	322	322
Personality Development [1]	Pearson Correlation	.546**	.469**	.518**	-.030	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.587	
	N	322	322	322	322	322

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The correlation analysis provides significant information about the association among variables with respect to strength and direction in relationships amid the research variables under study. The results revealed

significant information about the association among the research variables which has been confirmed through correlation procedure for analyzing the variables as well as extracting the information. The results confirmed the association of predicting variables with the personality development like physical education ($R = .546$ & $P = .000$), creative self-efficacy ($R = .469$ & $P = .000$), student self-perception ($R = .518$ & $P = .000$), psychological depression ($R = -.030$ & $P = .000$), and thus hypothesis about the association was accepted from the outcomes of correlation procedure that provides the significant clues towards the regression procedure with the significant outcomes.

H2: There is significant impact of the physical education, creative self-efficacy, students' self-perception, and psychological depression on personality development (H2).

Regression Analysis

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R SEE
1	.677a	.458	.452	.44712

Regression Analysis (ANOVA)

Model		SS	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	53.641	4	13.410	67.079	.000b
	Residual	63.374	317	.200		
	Total	117.015	321			

Regression Analysis (Coefficients)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	SE	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.630	.215		2.929	.004
	Physical Education	.258	.036	.333	7.089	.000
	Creative Self-Efficacy	.207	.038	.251	5.475	.000
	Students' Self-Perception	.279	.042	.311	6.682	.000
	Psychological Depression	.059	.032	.077	1.826	.069

a. Predictors: Physical Education, Creative Self-Efficacy, Self-Perception & Depression

b. Dependent Variable: Personality Development

The regression procedure was used to examine the cause-&-effect relationship among research variables under consideration. The regression provides the outcomes about the prediction of the dependent variable over independent variables. The results of regression of study thus revealed significant impact and predictability of personality development through physical education, creative self-efficacy, students' self-perception, and psychological depression wherein the 45.8% change was occurred in personality development with the significant impact of the individual variables like physical education ($\beta = .258$ & $.000$), creative self-efficacy ($\beta = .207$ & $.000$), students' self-perception ($\beta = .279$ & $.000$), and psychological depression ($\beta = .259$ & $.069$), and thus hypothesis from the regression procedure and outcomes was accepted and substantiated in the current research study.

H3: There is significant mediating role of students' self-perception in relationship between physical education and personality development (H3).

First Mediation Steps (a)

Mediation Analysis

R	R-square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.4042	.1634	.3809	58.2709	1.0000	320.0000	.0000

Mediation Analysis

Model	Coefficient	se	T	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	2.2033	.1470	14.9835	.0000	1.9140	2.4926
Physical Education	.3494	.0458	7.6335	.0000	.2593	.4394

Predicting Variable: Physical Education

Criterion Variable: Students' Self-Perception

Second & Third Mediation Steps (b & c)

Mediation Analysis

R	R-square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.6357	.4041	.2186	122.7687	2.0000	319.0000	.0000

Mediation Analysis

Model	Coefficient	se	T	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.2613	.1347	9.3673	.0000	.9964	1.5262
Students' Self-Perception	.3189	.0545	5.8557	.0000	.2117	.4260
Physical Education	.3116	.0522	5.9712	.0000	.2089	.4143

Predicting Variable: Physical Education & Students' Self-Perception

Criterion Variable: Personality Development

DISCUSSION

The physical well-being is not the only result of physical education, as it leads to development of psychology and social aspects of character. The self-confidence developed in process of social interactions and physical education achievements helps in development of the personality [31]. Therefore, positive feedback improves self-perception, which encourages personality traits, such as extroversion and agreeableness that is linked with personality traits, such as openness to experience and innovation. Enhances self-esteem, social competence and mood control that are antecedents of the personality development [32]. The students who feel the sense of creativity capabilities are likely to be involved in activities that would promote personal development and self-expression, develop a feeling of intelligence, which are vital in molding their personality [33]. Thus, creative work promotes problem solving and critical thinking, are essential aspects of personality development.

The possessions of physical education and creative self-efficacy on personality development is a multidimensional process by which students develop psychological strength, social competence and emotional balance [34]. Physical education is important in the formation of personality as it offers students an opportunity to work together, participate in physical activities, and be goal-oriented that are required towards the desired determinations for the consequences [35]. The innovative efficacy of self, which is the concept that describes a viewpoint of the student in the ability to generate creative ideas and resolve problems in creative manner, further contributes to developing the personality as it stimulates curiosity, autonomy and adaptability [36]. Having the higher creative self-efficacy, students will be more inclined to be proactive, seek alternative solutions, and react to the challenges in constructive ways that will make them more open and flexible for developments.

Students who perceive themselves as competent and appreciated have higher chances of taking lesson learnt in physical education and creative activities, which will result in high self-esteem, confidence social competence [37]. On other hand, increased degree of depressive symptoms may hamper engagement, decrease self-confidence, and undermine beneficial impact of physical education and creative self-efficacy [38]. Depression may restrict the capacity of the students to view themselves in positive light and lower their desire to take initiative, which demonstrates interrelationships depict how positive developments in one area support positive developments in other areas, that promotes global transformation [39]. In general, the correlations between physical education and creative

self-efficacy, self-perception and psychological depression, and personality development are used to underline significance of considering student development as the complex process.

Recommendations

1. The institutions ought to have counseling services and mental support systems to help in detecting and minimizing psychological depression among students thus providing them with a support system that helps them view themselves positively and benefit as much as possible in their development.
2. The institution needs to reinforce physical education, combine creative learning actions to build the confidence, emotional stability and personal development of students so that not only physical activity but also the creative expression is to be regarded as mandatory part of the whole education.
3. The educational administration and policymakers ought to enable teacher training that focuses on importance of creativity self-efficacy and exercise in forming personalities and make sure that teaching methods are in line with strategies that facilitate psychological well-being of the students.
4. The extracurricular practices be planned by teachers and administrators in such a way that they active build positive self-perception over positive feedback, active participation and acknowledgement of the achievements of the students to strengthen their feelings of competence and self-esteem.

5.3 Directions for Future Research

1. The future studies may focus on other mediating and moderating factors like the family environment, peer support, emotional intelligence and institutional climate to determine a better picture of the multifaceted processes that determine self-perception and mental health of the students.
2. The future studies to consider longitudinal designs to study how physical education and creative self-efficacy affect the personality development with time so that scholars gain insight into causal association and psychological effects in the long-term in comparison to cross-sectional results.
3. The future research can follow the mixed-methods design will be quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews or observations to reveal more diverse insights into the lived experiences of students and a more representative picture of the development processes for the desired outcomes.

4. Comparative research in various regions, cultures, and education levels ought to be done to determine whether the relationship between physical education, creative self-efficacy, psychological depression along with personality developments is similar across various situations and contexts.

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